

Prevalence of allergic fungal rhinosinusitis among patients presented with nasal polyps

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Abstract:

Introduction: Allergic fungal rhinosinusitis (AFRS) is a noninvasive type of fungal rhinosinusitis (FRS) that is diagnosed by fulfilling five diagnostic criteria: type I hypersensitivity, nasal polyposis, characteristic findings on CT scan, presence of fungi on direct microscopy or culture, and allergic mucin containing fungal elements.

Objectives: This work aimed to study the fungal etiology of AFRS and to evaluate the prevalence of AFRS among patients with CRS with nasal polyposis (CRSwNP) that underwent endoscopic sinus surgery (ESS) at Sohag University Hospital.

Patients and Methods: A prospective study involved all patients presented to Otorhinolaryngology Department, Sohag University Hospital, Sohag, Egypt, with nasal polyposis and who were candidate for ESS during the period from December 2015 to December 2016. A detailed history was taken, full E.N.T examination and CT scans were done to all patients who underwent ESS. Histopathological examination of the removed polyps and eosinophilic allergic mucin (AM) was done using hematoxylin& eosin (H&E), periodic Acid schiff (PAS) and Gomorimethanamin silver (GMS) stains. Statistical analysis was carried out with the Statistical Software Package Standard (SPSS).

Results: In 17/61 patients, AM was detected, 12/61 of them (19.7%) showed no fungal hyphae and were diagnosed eosinophilic mucinrhinosinusitis (EMRS). In the remaining 5/61 (8.2%) cases AM and fungal hyphae were seen and diagnosed as AFRS. 41/61 (67.2%) patients didn't show neither AM nor fungal hyphae and diagnosed as CRSwNP. In 2/61 (3.3%) we detected fungal hyphae both on the surface of polyp mucosa and invading the tissue of the nasal polyps and diagnosed as chronic invasive fungal rhinosinusitis (CIFRS) and the remaining one patient (1/61=1.6%) was diagnosed to have inverted papilloma.

Conclusion: No significant association between AM and fungal hyphae, only 5/17 (P=0.09) patients with AM fulfill the diagnostic criteria of AFRS. The presence of AM is not unique to AFRS, but rather is the result of a process that could have other etiologies. AFRS is more appropriately termed allergic mucinous sinusitis or eosinophilic mucinous rhinosinusitis.

Ear to stay endoscope in assessment of middle ear cavity and surgical outcomes

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Abstract:

Introduction

The advent and development of endoscope in otology has opened new gateways for ear surgery. We have explored the current evidence to see the advantages of using endoscope exclusively or as an adjunct to microscope.

Aims And Objectives

The main objective of our study is to evaluate the use of endoscope alone and in conjunction with microscope for the anatomical and pathological assessment of middle ear cavity, for conduct of surgeries and to assess its outcomes.

Materials And Methods

This is a prospective study conducted in our hospital over the past year with a consolidation of 65 cases of chronic otitis media, which were diagnosed after relevant clinical, laboratory and radiological investigations. These patients were then subjected to endoscopic or endoscopy assisted microscopic ear surgery. 0 degree and 30 degree endoscopes were used to assess the tympanic membrane, ossicular chain status, middle ear mucosa and folds , disease pathology and apt surgical decisions were taken. Follow ups were conducted for a minimum period of 3 months.

Results

The use of endoscopes in ear surgeries have definitely proven to have opened new frontiers in otology and has made surgery more finite, the surgeons more confident and the outcome better.

Conclusion

Endoscopes have revolutionized the world of otology in the following ways – better visualization of the recesses of the middle ear cleft, minimal dissection of normal tissue, reduced cholesteatoma recidivism rates, reduction in second look surgery, helping preserve the canal wall, increase in the surgeon's confidence in total cholesteatoma removal and even a change to the post cholesteatoma follow up protocols.

Bilateral Pneumothorax Post Emergency Airway Intervention

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Abstract:

We present the experience we encountered in a rare case of Bilateral Pneumothorax Post Airway Intervention.

A patient with diffuse axonal injury, with compound type 2 fracture of left tibia and fat embolism, post road traffic accident, was taken up for tracheostomy. He was diagnosed to have developed bilateral pneumothorax following the procedure, which according to literature has been of rare incidence. The causes of the pneumothorax following the procedure could be attributed to a tear or trauma in the posterior tracheal wall while inserting the tube or due to the rupture of alveolar bullae or bleb.

Keywords:

Pneumothorax, Tracheostomy, Posterior tracheal wall injury, Alveolar bleb, Positive pressure ventilation

Biography :

Hailing from Dubai, I did my under graduation (MBBS) in Vydehi Institute of Medical Sciences, Bangalore, and am right now doing my final year post graduation for MS in ENT in Kempegowda Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Centre, Bangalore both of which are affiliated to the RGUHS University, Karnataka, India.

I have published 3 articles in 2 different journals of which 2 of my articles including a research article, were published in the esteemed IJOHNS. I have various other works of mine waiting to be approved and published too.

I have attended various state and national conferences and have got to present a paper and a poster in 1 of them. I have got the opportunities to help in the organization of national level ENT conferences in our college. This would be the first ever international conference outside India I would be getting to be a part of and I am looking forward to it with immense excitement.

Being a post graduate, I look for opportunities and platforms that can quench my thirst for learning and improving myself in all the fields of medicine and hence, I see this platform as one of those and take privilege in being able to be a part of it.

Inferior Turbinate Reduction - Comparative Study

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Abstract:

Background:

Inferior turbinate hypertrophy is one of the most common causes of nasal obstruction .Many different surgical methods are available for treatment of this condition .

Study design and objectives:

This is a comparative retrospective study carried out on patients who underwent surgical turbinate reduction of the inferior turbinates in the period between March 2015 and March 2017.

This study compares between the rate of complications between partial inferior turbinectomy and endoscopic powered turbinoplasty. The study carried out at Otolaryngology department,at Ad Diwanyia teaching hospital , Diwanyia city, Iraq.

Results:

A total of 50 patients with nasal obstruction had been included in this study. The patients were divided into two groups. The first group treated by surgical inferior turbinectomy while the second group by powered endoscopic turbinoplasty. The gender distribution was (15 (52%) male and 10(48 %) female and 14(48%) male and 11(62 %)female) for the first and second group respectively with no significant difference between the two groups($p>0.05$) . The mean age of first group was 27.40 ± 7.7 years while the mean age of second group was 26.68 ± 6.82 years with no significant difference between the two groups ($p>0.05$).There is significant difference between the two groups in occurrence of severe bleeding and crustation which is higher in group 1 ($p<0.05$).There is no statistically significant difference in atrophic rhinitis but it is clinically important.

Conclusion:

Powered endoscopic turbinoplasty associated with less post-operative complications than partial inferior turbinectomy

Biography:

Wasam A. Albusalih had been graduated from college of medicine in Baghdad 1999, Degreed in Otorhinolaryngology Head and neck surgery in 2013 , interested much in endoscopic sinus surgery since that , I did more than 100 successful DCR and about 500 endoscopic sinus operations with few endoscopic skull base operations in last 3 years at Diwanyia , Iraq.

Endoscopic DCR VS LASER-Assisted DCR - Comparative Study

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Abstract:

Design:

Prospective interventional clinical trial study for 24 months (from February 2013 to February 2015) at Diwanyia teaching hospital.

Subject:

Fifty patients aged 10-62 years with chronic nasolacrimal duct obstruction not resolved by conservative measures.

Methods:

All the patients were received medical treatment and conservative measures for several weeks before starting surgical treatment, then patient divided into two groups:

Group 1: treated by endonasal DCR (25 patients).

Group 2: treated by endonasal laser-assisted DCR (25 patients).

The procedure was performed under general anesthesia for both groups. In both groups bicanalicular silicone stent was used, success of procedure was determined by the absence of epiphora (subjective) and patency of lacrimal system on irrigation (objective). Patients in both groups followed for 7-14 months.

Result:

Endonasal DCR was done to 25 patients (group 1), and endonasal assisted- DCR for 25 patients (group2) , the average time of procedure in group 1 was 38 minutes, while in group 2 was 25 minutes ,the silicone stent was removed 4-6 months after the surgery. Absence of epiphora was in 20 patients out of 25 (80%) in group 1 , while it was in 16 patients out of 25 (64%) in group 2 which was significant ($P<0.001$).

Five patients in group 1 develop postoperative adhesion (20%), while in group 2 was 9 patients (36%).All recurrent cases in group 1 due to adhesions , after revision surgery only 2 patients improved raising the success rate to 88% , in group 2 two patients improved after revision surgery raising success rate to 72% .

Conclusion:

We conclude that endonasal DCR is effective as is endonasal laser assisted DCR with higher success rate in the former , but with lesser time in the later.

Biography:

Wasam A. Albusalih had been graduated from college of medicine in Baghdad 1999, Degreed in Otorhinolaryngology Head and neck surgery in 2013 , interested much in endoscopic sinus surgery since that , I did more than 100 successful DCR and about 500 endoscopic sinus operations with few endoscopic skull base operations in last 3 years at Diwanyia , Iraq.